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Development of a Bipropellant HTP - Propane Propulsion Subsystem for EARS (European Advanced Reusable Satellite) Program.**Lorenzo Gerolin^{a*}, Giulia Quinzi^b, Francesco Barato^c**^a *Technology for Propulsion and Innovation, Via Emilia 15, Monselice (PD), Italy 35043, l.gerolin@t4innovation.com*^b *Technology for Propulsion and Innovation, Via Emilia 15, Monselice (PD), Italy 35043, g.quinzi@t4innovation.com*^c *Università degli Studi di Padova, Via Venezia 1, Padova (PD), Italy 35131, francesco.barato@unipd.it** *Corresponding author***Abstract**

EARS is a Horizon Europe program funded by the European Commission that lays the basis for a European reusable satellite that carries scientific and commercial payloads to orbit and then safely retrieves them back on Earth. The leading entity is the National Institute of Applied Physics of the Italian Research Council. The other partners are Kongsberg Nanoavionics, Von Karman Institute, Deimos, the University of Padova and T4i - Technology for Propulsion and Innovation. T4i contribution to the program is the development of a High Test Peroxide (>90%) and propane propulsion subsystem that deorbits the spacecraft, using differential steering to keep the thrust aligned with the velocity direction. A gaseous propane fed Roll Control System (RoCS) has been included in the system to account for the roll motion around the principal thrust axis of the satellite, complementing the differential steering work performed by the main thrusters. The propulsion subsystem is composed of 4 identical modules that are installed in the aft section of the satellite. Each module is composed of a propane tank, a HTP tank, one bipropellant thruster, two cold gas nozzles, the fluidics, and an electronic board. The propane vapor pressure is used to self-pressurize the whole system, simplifying the architecture and eliminating the use of a third fluid as pressurant. A discharge code was developed to simulate the behavior of the fluidic system from tanks to thruster. Different geometrical and thermophysical aspects have been considered, including pressure losses due to both vaporization of propane and the passage through valves and orifices at different tank starting temperatures and pressures. The key strategy determined from the simulations is to extract gaseous propane to feed the RoCS nozzles and to drain liquid propane to feed the engines. Employing this solution lowers the amount of power to be given to the propane tank to sustain the whole discharge within the expected propane temperature range. After considerations on the behaviour of the fluidic discharges, the physical layout of the propulsion subsystem was drafted, and the fluidic ground support infrastructure was designed, built, and tested to perform the experimental campaign of the main thruster.

Acronyms

<i>CG</i>	Cold Gas
<i>EARS</i>	European Advanced Reusable Satellite
<i>GNC</i>	Guidance, Navigation and Control
<i>HTP</i>	High Test Peroxide
<i>LEO</i>	Low Earth Orbit
<i>O/F</i>	Oxidizer to Fuel Ratio
<i>Pr</i>	Prandtl Number
<i>Re</i>	Reynolds Number
<i>SG</i>	Specific Gravity
<i>T4i</i>	Technology for Propulsion and Innovation

Symbols

<i>A</i>	Area
<i>C</i>	Model Constants
<i>c</i>	Heat Capacity, Speed of Sound
<i>c*</i>	Characteristic Velocity

<i>D</i>	Diameter
<i>F</i>	Two Phase Multiplier
<i>f</i>	Fraction of Vapour in Tank
<i>g</i>	Gravity
<i>H</i>	Enthalpy
<i>h</i>	Heat Exchange Coefficient
<i>K</i>	Flow Factor, Model Variable
<i>k</i>	Specific Heats Ratio
<i>L</i>	Length
<i>M</i>	Molar Mass, Mach Number
<i>m</i>	Mass
<i>p</i>	Pressure
<i>Q</i>	Heat
<i>q</i>	Thermal Power
<i>R</i>	Gas Constant, Thermal Resistance
<i>r</i>	Radius
<i>S</i>	Entropy
<i>s</i>	Specific Entropy

T	Temperature, Thrust
t	Time, Thickness
V	Volume
X	Lockart-Martinelli parameter (X_{tt})
x	Vapour Quality, Length Discretization

α	Convective Coefficient
β	Boiling Model Parameter
Δ	Variation
ϵ	Roughness
λ	Thermal Conductivity
μ	Dynamic Viscosity
ξ	Friction Factor
ρ	Density
v	Specific Volume
ω	Bartz Gas Coefficient

Subscripts

0	Reference Condition
<i>cat</i>	Catalyst
<i>cb</i>	Convective Boiling
<i>cc</i>	Combustion Chamber
<i>cond</i>	Conductive
<i>conv</i>	Convective
<i>cumul</i>	Cumulative
<i>e</i>	Exit
<i>f</i>	Fuel, Nozzle Coefficient (c_f)
<i>g</i>	Gas
<i>l</i>	Liquid, Lateral
<i>nb</i>	Nucleate Boiling
<i>noz</i>	Nozzle
<i>r</i>	Ratio
<i>rc</i>	Regenerative Channel
<i>t</i>	Time
<i>v</i>	Vapour

Superscripts

0	Reference Condition
<i>b</i>	Burning
<i>BP</i>	Bipropellant
<i>CG</i>	Cold Gas
<i>e</i>	Exit
<i>EV</i>	To be Evaporated to Maintain Pressure
<i>in</i>	Inlet
<i>inj</i>	Injection
<i>max</i>	Maximum
<i>prop</i>	Propellant
<i>res</i>	Residual
<i>th</i>	Throat
<i>TOT</i>	Total

Fig. 1. EARS satellite render in orbit.

1. Introduction

The New Space Economy is driving advancements in sustainability, cost efficiency, and reduced time to orbit, paving the way for the development of next-generation launch systems and space vehicles. A key aspect of this shift is the growing emphasis on reusability. In this context, EARS has been conceived as a recoverable and reusable microsatellite, designed to transport small payloads back and forth to Low Earth Orbit (LEO) [1] [2] [3].

The reference satellite for the EARS design is the Kongsberg NanoAvionics MP42. The MP42 platform supports subsystem expansions, and in the case of EARS, this includes the integration of two additional modules: one for the inflatable re-entry heatshield [4] and one for the propulsion subsystem, which also includes a deployable parafoil [5] to slow down the descent of the satellite in the atmosphere (Fig. 1).

The EARS propulsion system uses green propellants to minimize costs, environmental impact, and operational complexity. High-concentration hydrogen peroxide was chosen as the oxidizer due to its moderate cost, high density, possible storage in space at moderate pressures, and its ability to be decomposed in a catalyst bed without preheating. This enables both monopropellant and staged-combustion bipropellant configurations [6]. Propane was selected as fuel for its low cost, wide availability, good performance, and moderate self-pressurization at room temperature. This self-pressurization feature supports a simplified two-fluid system, eliminating the need for a third pressurizing gas and associated components, like pressure regulators [7].

The propulsion subsystem for the EARS satellite consists of four chemical propulsion units [8], each of which includes a combustion chamber, a catalytic bed, valves, fluidic lines, a hydrogen peroxide tank and a propane tank. The total volume of a tank comprises the following com-

ponents:

- **usable propellant volume:** it is the volume of tank required to hold the usable propellant mass;
- **ullage volume:** it is the volume of tank left unfilled to allow for expansion of the propellant or contraction of the tank structure;
- **trapped volume:** it is the volume of unusable propellant left in the tank at the end of the engine operation.

The total tank volume is the sum of the previous elements.

EARS propulsion is a blowdown self-pressurized system, meaning that the fuel serves as pressurizing element for the HTP. This solution is simpler in design, has fewer parts, and usually weighs less than a pressure-regulated system; however, the main general drawback of this type of pressurisation is that the tank pressure continuously drops throughout the firing timeline if no additional thermal power is given to the system. The main consequence is that the thruster performance changes according to the tank pressure variation over the lifetime. In the EARS case, the pressurizer element is the propane, which inside its own tank is characterised by an equilibrium between the liquid phase and the vapour phase. The pressure that defines this condition is called vapour pressure and depends solely on the temperature of the propane. Propane has a moderate pressure (not too high or low) at room temperature (10 bar at 25°C), which makes it a suitable option for EARS.

The propane tank communicates with the hydrogen peroxide tank and at the same time with the combustion chamber. Initially, within its own tank, the vapour phase of propane will be in equilibrium with the liquid phase. However, upon system activation, hydrogen peroxide will start to flow, and because of the hydrogen peroxide leaving its tank, the liquid propane will flow into the HTP tank and in the fluid line toward the combustion chamber. Therefore, the propane vapour phase will expand inside its tank and, as a consequence, there will be a reduction of the propane vapour pressure, that the system will attempt to compensate for by evaporating a certain amount of liquid propane. The heat needed by the liquid propane to evaporate is given by the product of the enthalpy of vaporisation H and the mass of propane evaporated $m_{f,v}$:

$$Q = m_{f,v}H \quad [1]$$

Under standard conditions, this heat is drawn from the liquid propane itself, causing it to cool. However, a reduction of the propane temperature will consequently result in a decreasing vapour pressure. This is why, as previously mentioned, the tank discharge pressure does not remain constant over time but slowly decreases. In order to limit

the pressure tank variation, and thus the performance over time, the propane tank is supplied with a heating power through electric resistances. To prevent contact of HTP with propane, the HTP tank is equipped with a special mechanical interface that acts as a barrier between the two substances (Fig. 2).

Regarding the liquid propane conveyed to the combustion chamber, it will first pass through two valves and then through a regenerative channel wrapped around the nozzle throat, to vaporise. Finally, the propane in its vapour phase will be injected into the chamber by means of a converging-diverging nozzle to choke the flow. As for HTP, once it exits the tank, it passes through two valves before being introduced into the decomposition chamber. Inside this chamber, it comes into contact with the catalytic bed that decomposes the HTP into hot oxygen and steam. Subsequently, the decomposition products are injected into the combustion chamber always through a converging-diverging nozzle, effectively controlling the flow.

Fig. 2. General operating diagram of the propulsion unit.

The aim of the following sections is to explain the models implemented to simulate the behaviour of a single propulsion unit. In particular, the main aspects that need to be modelled to predict the performance of the system along the burning time are:

- the **HTP and propane discharges** from their tanks;
- the **pressure losses** of both propane and HTP along the respective fluidic lines;
- the **injection** into the combustion chamber

2. Tank discharge model

The purpose of the tank discharge model is to predict the evolution over time of the pressure and temperature inside the tank. The main input parameters required by the model are:

- the initial tank temperature T_{tank}^0 - once it has been defined, it will be possible to compute all the propane initial thermodynamic properties, such as density and specific entropy of the liquid phase ($\rho_{f,l}^0, s_{f,l}^0$) and of the vapour phase ($\rho_{f,v}^0, s_{f,v}^0$), the HTP initial density ρ_{HTP}^0 and the initial tank pressure p_{tank}^0 , which is equal to the saturation pressure of propane, therefore it will solely depend on the temperature inside the tank;
- the thermal power q provided to the propane tank;
- the initial mass of liquid propane loaded into the tank for bipropellant use $m_{f,l}^{BP}$;
- the mass of liquid propane for CG system $m_{f,l}^{CG}$ - once it will be converted into vapour, it will supply the cold gas thrusters responsible for the attitude control;
- the maximum operating temperature of the tank T_{tank}^{max} - it allows to determine the density of the liquid ($\rho_{f,l}^{max}$) and vapour ($\rho_{f,v}^{max}$) in this particular condition;
- the initial fraction of propane vapour phase f , with respect to the total volume of the propane tank.

By freezing the previous input variables, it is possible to compute the volume of the propane tank as the sum of the volume occupied by the liquid phase and the vapour phase at the maximum operating temperature. A liquid propane mass contribution $m_{f,l}^{EV}$ must be added to account for the need of self-pressurization of the gas, which is more intense at high temperature, leaving more gaseous residuals when warmer than when colder. It is worth noting that this residual mass can be used as added cold gas propellant after the end of the bipropellant thrusters operations. The $m_{f,l}^{EV}$ mass is calculated considering no final liquid residuals at the maximum operating temperature. Notably, the tank volume is determined by the maximum temperature of the system because, as the temperature increases, the propane liquid density decreases. Consequently, for the same mass and low vapor fractions, the occupied volume increases. The volume of fuel is the sum of the liquid and vapor phases:

$$V_{tank,f} = V_{f,l} + V_{f,v} \quad [2]$$

where the volume of the propane liquid phase is computed as:

$$V_{f,l} = \frac{m_{f,l}^{CG} + m_{f,l}^{BP} + m_{f,l}^{EV}}{\rho_{f,l}^{max}} \quad [3]$$

while the volume of the propane vapour phase is the product of the fraction of propane vapour phase with the total volume of the propane tank:

$$V_{f,v} = f \cdot V_{tank,f} = \frac{f}{1-f} \cdot V_{f,l} \quad [4]$$

Consequently, the mass of the initial vapour phase of propane is:

$$m_{f,v} = V_{f,v} \cdot \rho_{f,v}^{max} \quad [5]$$

Finally, the total mass of liquid propane initially stored in the tank is:

$$m_{f,l}^{tank} = m_{f,l}^{CG} + m_{f,l}^{BP} + m_{f,l}^{EV} \quad [6]$$

while the total mass of propane in the tank is:

$$m_f^{tank} = m_{f,l}^{tank} + m_{f,v} \quad [7]$$

The initial mass of HTP is related to that of the fuel ($m_{f,l}^{BP}$) by the O/F ratio:

$$m_{HTP} = O/F \cdot m_{f,l}^{BP} \quad [8]$$

in which the mass of the propane residuals does not participate in the definition of the mass of HTP.

Another initial parameter is the quality of vapour. From the following relation:

$$\nu = \nu_v \cdot x_0 + \nu_l \cdot (1 - x_0) \quad [9]$$

where ν , ν_v and ν_l are respectively the specific volume of all the propane, of the vapour phase and of the liquid phase, the quality of vapour can be derived as:

$$x_0 = \frac{\nu - \frac{1}{\rho_{f,l}}}{\frac{1}{\rho_{f,v}} - \frac{1}{\rho_{f,l}}} \quad [10]$$

The last initial parameter is the entropy, which can be computed as:

$$S_0 = m_f^{tank} \cdot [(1 - x_0)s_l + x_0s_v] \quad [11]$$

Now, the propane discharge from its tank into the one of the HTP will be described from a thermodynamic perspective by considering a control volume that coincides with the boundaries of the propane total volume in the tanks, and by writing the thermodynamic balances at that control volume. The entropy balance states that the change in entropy of the system, summed with the change in entropy due to the outflow of liquid propane in the combustion chamber, must equal the ratio of the thermal power

supplied to the system to its temperature:

$$dS + dm \cdot s_{f,l} = \frac{q}{T} \quad [12]$$

For what concerns the mass balance instead, the mass variation of the system must equal the propane mass flow rate times the infinitesimal time step:

$$dm = -\dot{m}_{f,l} \cdot dt \quad [13]$$

therefore, the mass left in the tank must be equal to the total propane mass minus the propane mass that has left the tank after a certain time. Finally, the propane complete volume at each iteration can be computed as follow:

$$V_{tank,f}^{t+dt} = V_{tank,f}^t + \frac{\Delta m_{HTP}}{\rho_{HTP}} \quad [14]$$

where Δm_{HTP} is the HTP mass expelled after the time step Δt and m_f^{tank} is the actual mass of fuel in the tank. The model objectives is to determine temperature, pressure and vapour quality with time. Therefore, at each time step, these quantities are obtained by solving the following system of equations, knowing that both specific entropy and specific volume are function of temperature and vapour quality indeed:

$$\begin{cases} s(x, T) = x \cdot s_{f,v}(T) + (1-x) \cdot s_{f,l}(T) \\ \nu(x, T) = x \cdot \nu_{f,v}(T) + (1-x) \cdot \nu_{f,l}(T) \end{cases} \quad [15]$$

Once the temperature is known, the pressure p_{tank} can be also determined at each time step.

3. Fluidic losses model

3.1 Propane fluidic line

The pressure loss along the propane fluidic line is the sum of the following contributes:

- the pressure losses over the two valves;
- the pressure loss over the regenerative channel.

$$\Delta p_f = 2 \cdot \Delta p_{valve} + \Delta p_{rc} \quad [16]$$

For what concerns the pressure losses over the valves, they can be computed as:

$$\Delta p_{valve,f} = SG_f \cdot \left(\frac{\dot{v}_f}{K} \right)^2 \quad [17]$$

where \dot{v}_f is the propane volumetric flow rate:

$$\dot{v}_f = \frac{\dot{m}_f}{\rho_f} \quad [18]$$

SG_f is called 'specific gravity' and it represents the ratio between propane and water density:

$$SG_f = \frac{\rho_f}{\rho_{H_2O}} \quad [19]$$

Finally, K is the flow factor, equal to:

$$K = 0.865 C_v \quad [20]$$

where C_v is the flow coefficient.

Moving on to the regenerative channel, the reason for its presence is to vaporize the propane, thanks to the heat exchanged between the high-temperature nozzle wall and the propellant inside the channel itself. The importance of vaporising the propane before it enters the combustion chamber stems from the fact that if the propane is injected in its liquid state, it would suffer from poor atomization at the moment of injection into the chamber due to the low pressure budget available for the atomization process. Moreover, the difficulties to manufacture the very small holes compatible with the tiny liquid flow favor the selection of the gaseous solution. It is interesting to assess the pressure decrease of propane following its passage through the regenerative channel. To do this, it is necessary to first calculate the equilibrium temperatures of the regenerative channel walls and the heat exchanged by them as function of the propane vapour quality. The initial parameters that need to be defined are:

- the critical pressure at the nozzle throat: $p^* = p_{cc} \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2}\right)^{\frac{-k}{k-1}}$;
- the critical temperature at the throat: $T^* = T_{cc} \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2}\right)$;
- the combustion gas density at the throat: $\rho^* = \rho_{cc} \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2}\right)^{\frac{-1}{k-1}}$;
- the speed of sound at the throat: $c = \sqrt{kRT^*}$;
- the conductivity λ_{noz} , the specific heat at constant pressure $c_{p,noz}$, the Prandtl number Pr_{noz} and the dynamic viscosity $\mu_{noz} = \frac{Pr_{noz} \lambda_{noz}}{c_{p,noz}}$ at the nozzle throat;
- the regenerative channel section $A_{rc} = \frac{\pi D_{rc}^2}{4}$;

In particular, there are three heat transfers that need to be taken into account: the convective heat transfer from the hot gases in the nozzle throat to the nozzle internal wall $q_{conv,1}$, the conductive heat transfer between the nozzle wall and the regenerative channel wall q_{cond} and the convective heat transfer between the latter and the fuel in the regenerative channel $q_{conv,2}$:

$$q_{conv,1} = A_{l,rc} \cdot \alpha \cdot (T_{g,noz} - T_{wall,noz}^i) \quad [21]$$

$$q_{cond} = \frac{A_{l,rc} \lambda}{t} (T_{wall,noz}^i - T_{wall,noz}^e) \quad [22]$$

$$q_{conv,2} = A_{l,rc} \cdot h \cdot (T_{wall,noz}^e - T_f) \quad [23]$$

By considering the global thermal resistance of the heat transfer (Fig. 3), which can be written as:

$$R = \frac{1}{\alpha A_{l,rc}} + \frac{t}{\lambda A_{l,rc}} + \frac{1}{h A_{l,rc}} \quad [24]$$

the heat transferred from the combustion gases inside the nozzle throat to the fuel inside the regenerative channel can be expressed as:

$$q_{global} = \frac{T_{g,noz} - T_f}{R} \quad [25]$$

Fig. 3. Representation of the heat exchanged between the gas inside the nozzle throat and the propane inside the regenerative channel.

For what concern the correlations employed to compute the convective heat transfer coefficients, the one related to the convective heat transfer from the gas inside the nozzle to the nozzle wall is computed as:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \sigma \cdot \left(\frac{A_{th}}{A}\right)^{0.9} \left(\frac{0.026}{D_{th}^{0.2}}\right) \left(\frac{\mu^{0.2} \cdot c_{p,th}}{Pr_{th}^{0.6}}\right) \left(\frac{p_{cc}}{c^*}\right)^{0.8} \left(\frac{D_{th}}{r_{th,c}}\right)^{0.1} \\ \sigma = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{T_{wall,noz}^i}{T_{g,noz}} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2}\right)\right]^{0.8-0.2 \cdot \omega}} \end{cases} \quad [26]$$

where $r_{th,c} = 1.5r_{th}$ is the nozzle curvature radius at throat. The coefficient related to the convective heat exchange between the regenerative channel wall and the propane was calculated via the following two-phase flow boiling model [9]:

$$h_{tp} = \left(h_{nb}^{C_{14}} + (F \cdot h_{cb})^{C_{14}}\right)^{\frac{1}{C_{14}}} \quad [27]$$

$$h_{cb} = C_{11} \cdot Re_{f,l}^{C_{12}} \cdot Pr_{f,l}^{C_{13}} \cdot \left(\frac{k_l}{D_h}\right) \quad [28]$$

$$h_{nb} = C_6 \cdot p_r^{C_7} \cdot (-\log(p_r))^{C_8} \cdot M^{C_9} \cdot Q^{C_{10}} \quad [29]$$

$$F = 1 + C_4 \cdot X_{tt}^{C_5} \quad [30]$$

$$X_{tt} = \left(\frac{1-x}{x}\right)^{C_1} \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_{f,v}}{\rho_{f,l}}\right)^{C_2} \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{f,l}}{\mu_{f,v}}\right)^{C_3} \quad [31]$$

In particular, h_{cb} is the convective boiling heat transfer coefficient, h_{nb} the nucleate flow boiling heat transfer

efficient, F the two-phase multiplier, X_{tt} the Lockart-Martinelli parameter and p_r is the ratio between the propane saturation pressure and the critic pressure. The C_i coefficients represent optimised correlation constants, specific for the proposed boiling model. The coefficient h depends on the vapour quality and, specifically in the correlation adopted, h increases with increasing vapour qualities until the occurrence of the dry-out, and then decreases are observed. Moreover, increasing mass fluxes and heat fluxes increases the flow boiling heat transfer coefficient rates.

Once the global heat transfer has been computed as a function of the propane vapour quality, the nozzle wall temperature and the one of the regenerative channel wall can be computed as follow:

$$\begin{cases} T_{wall,noz}^i = T_{g,noz} - \frac{q}{\alpha A_{rc}} \\ T_{wall,noz}^e = T_{tank}^0 + \frac{q}{h A_{rc}} \end{cases} \quad [32]$$

The next step is the calculation of the minimum length of the regenerative channel to ensure the complete vaporisation of propane and, consequently, the pressure drop experienced by propane as it passes through the channel. In order to do so, the regenerative channel has been discretized in a certain number of cells and an iterative cycle has been implemented. The main input parameters required by the model are:

- the length step Δx for channel axial discretization;
- the section of the regenerative channel: $A_{rc} = \frac{\pi D_{rc}^2}{4} m^2$;
- the initial vapour quality: $x_0 = 0.01$;
- the lateral surface of a single cell: $A_{cell} = \pi D_{rc} \Delta x m^2$;

As long as the propane vapour quality $x < 1$, meaning until the propane has completely vaporised, at each iteration the length of the regenerative channel is incremented of the quantity Δx and the pressure loss per unit length is computed as follows:

$$\Delta p_{dl} = \left(\xi \cdot \frac{m_j^2}{2\rho_{f,v} D_{rc}}\right) \left[1 + x \left(\frac{\rho_{f,l}}{\rho_{f,v}} - 1\right)\right] \left[2 - x \left(\frac{\rho_{f,l}}{\rho_{f,v}} - 1\right) - 1\right] (K_2 - 1) \quad [33]$$

where ξ is the friction factor that can be computed by solving numerically the Colebrook - White Equation:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\xi}} + 2 \log \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{3.7 \cdot D_{rc}} + \frac{2.51}{Re \cdot \sqrt{\varepsilon}} \right) \quad [34]$$

where ε is the roughness of the regenerative channel wall

and K_2 is a coefficient that depends on $\beta = \frac{x\rho_{f,i}}{(1-x)\rho_{f,v}}$:

$$K_2 = \begin{cases} 1 + 0.09 \cdot \beta & \text{if } \beta \leq 0.4 \\ 1 - \frac{\frac{2.97}{\beta^{2/3}+1}}{6 \left(\frac{1.83}{\beta^{2/3}+1} \right) \left(\frac{3.43}{\beta^{2/3}+1} \right)} & \text{if } \beta > 0.4 \end{cases} \quad [35]$$

and Re is the Reynolds number, defined as

$$Re = \frac{\rho v D_{rc}}{\mu} \quad [36]$$

where the velocity in the regenerative channel can be written as function of the propane mass flow rate and of the section of the regenerative channel $v = \frac{\dot{m}_f}{\rho A_{rc}}$ and the dynamic viscosity as function of the vapour quality:

$$Re = \frac{4\dot{m}_f}{\pi D_{rc} \cdot [\mu_{f,i}(1-x) + x\mu_{f,v}]} \quad [37]$$

At each iteration, the actual pressure loss is updated adding the following term to the pressure loss cumulated so far:

$$\Delta p_{dl} \cdot \Delta x \quad [38]$$

The heat exchanged between the nozzle and the regenerative channel on each cell can be computed as:

$$Q = t_{avg} \cdot \dot{q} \cdot A_{cell} \quad [39]$$

where \dot{q} is the rate of heat exchanged per unit of surface and it is a function of the vapour quality, while $t_{avg} = \frac{\Delta x A_{rc} \rho}{\dot{m}_f}$ is the average residence time of propane in a single cell, considering the density as a weighted average on the two phases with their respective densities. Then, the evaporated mass of propane in each cell is:

$$m_{f,evap} = \frac{Q}{H} \quad [40]$$

where H is the propane vaporisation enthalpy. The new mass of vapour propane will be given as an update of the one calculated for the previous iteration, as well as for vapour quality and the overall heat exchanged by the fluid along the regenerative channel. The iterations will continue until the value of the vapour quality value reaches one. At this point, the real pressure loss along the regenerative channel and its required length are known.

3.2 Hydrogen peroxide fluidic line

The pressure loss along the HTP fluidic line is the sum of the following contributes:

- the pressure losses over the two valves;
- the pressure loss over the injection plate of the catalytic bed;
- the pressure loss due to the catalytic bed.

$$\Delta p_{HTP} = 2 \cdot \Delta p_{valve} + \Delta p_{inj} + \Delta p_{cat} \quad [41]$$

The pressure loss across the single valve can be computed in the same way as for propane with equations from (17) to (19) adapted to the HTP case. For what concern the pressure loss across the injection plate, it can be computed by combining the mass flow rate definition with the Bernoulli principle:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{m}_{HTP} = \rho_{HTP} \cdot v_{inj} \cdot A_{inj} \\ \Delta p_{inj} = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{HTP} v_{inj}^2 \end{cases} \quad [42]$$

Two other factors have to be considered. The first one is that the real mass flow rate is slightly lower than the previous one, therefore \dot{m}_{HTP} needs to be multiplied by the discharge coefficient C_d , which is determined experimentally. Therefore, the actual mass flow rate is $\dot{m}_{HTP,real} = C_d \cdot \dot{m}_{HTP}$. The second one is that the injection area depends on the geometry of the injection plate, and in particular is a function of the number of holes and of their diameter:

$$A_{inj} = n_{holes} \cdot \frac{\pi D_{holes}^2}{4} \quad [43]$$

The pressure drop across the injection plate is derived by the combination of the equations (42) and (43):

$$\Delta p_{inj} = \frac{\dot{m}_{HTP,real}^2}{C_d^2 n^2 A_{inj}^2 2 \rho_{HTP}} \quad [44]$$

To conclude, the pressure loss due to the catalytic bed has been preliminary supposed constant since the variation of the pressure losses within the catalyst itself requires an experimental-based characterisation which will be carried on in a later phase.

4. Injection model

As it has already been mentioned, both propane and HTP enter the combustion chamber in the gaseous state; the first one thanks to the passage through the regenerative channel and the second one thanks to the decomposition triggered by the catalytic bed. To regulate the mass flow of propane and hydrogen peroxide as a linear function of upstream pressure, converging-diverging nozzles are used in EARS. As a result, the mass flow rate is determined using the principles of gas dynamics by modeling the injectors as nozzles. Subsequently, the magnitude of the mass flow rate is analysed based on the downstream conditions of the injection. The main input data required by the model are:

- the geometry of the nozzles, which comprises the throat areas ($A_{inj,f}^{th}$, $A_{inj,HTP}^{th}$), and the expansion ratio of the nozzle ε , from which the exit areas ($A_{inj,f}^e$, $A_{inj,HTP}^e$) are automatically defined;
- the pressures of both propane and HTP before injection.

tion, which are lower than the pressure tank because of the pressure losses along the fluidic line:

$$\begin{cases} p_{inj,f}^{in} = p_{tank} - \Delta p_f \\ p_{inj,HTP}^{in} = p_{tank} - \Delta p_{HTP} \end{cases} \quad [45]$$

where the pressure losses are obtained via the fluidic losses model (equations (16) and (41) respectively).

The first step involves solving the nozzle, or more precisely, determining the two ways in which the flow evolves isentropically within it, once the critical condition is reached at the throat, in terms of Mach number and pressure at the exit section. The isentropic equation that follows relates the geometry of the nozzle to the Mach number:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{M_e} \left[\frac{2 \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_e^2 \right)}{k+1} \right]^{\frac{k+1}{2(k-1)}} \quad [46]$$

therefore, given the areas of the nozzle's exit section and throat section, it is possible to derive the Mach number at the exit section under subsonic ($M_{e,sub}$) and supersonic ($M_{e,sup}$) conditions for both propane and hydrogen peroxide. Once the Mach numbers are known and assuming that the stagnation pressure upstream of the injection coincides with $p_{inj,f}^{in}$ and $p_{inj,HTP}^{in}$ for the propane and HTP lines, respectively, it is possible to calculate the pressure at the exit section of the injector under subsonic and supersonic conditions:

$$\begin{cases} p_{inj,sub}^e = p_{inj}^{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{e,sub}^2 \right)^{\frac{-k}{k-1}} \\ p_{inj,sup}^e = p_{inj}^{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_{e,sup}^2 \right)^{\frac{-k}{k-1}} \end{cases} \quad [47]$$

At this point, the evolution followed by the fluid in the divergent part of the nozzle will depend on the entity of the discharge pressure, that is the combustion chamber pressure p_{cc} , with respect to the critical pressure of the nozzle, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Consequently, three distinct scenarios may arise:

1. *the pressure chamber p_{cc} is comprised between p_{inj}^{in} and $p_{inj,sub}^e$:*

obviously p_{cc} can't be higher than p_{inj}^{in} , otherwise there would be no flow. In this case the throat will not be choked and the divergent part of the injector will undergo subsonic conditions. As a result, at the exit section of the nozzle perfect adaptation will occur, which means that the exit pressure matches that of the combustion chamber. The actual Mach number at the exit section can be found by solving equation (47) in terms of the Mach number, by imposing $p_{inj}^e = p_{cc}$. Next, the mass flow rate can be com-

puted as:

$$\dot{m} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{R}} \frac{p_{inj}^{in}}{\sqrt{T_{tank}}} \frac{M_e}{\left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_e^2 \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(k-1)}}} \cdot A_e \quad [48]$$

2. *the pressure chamber is comprised between $p_{inj,sub}^e$ and $p_{cc,lim}$:*

in this particular situation, the normal shock wave will move inward within the divergent section until it degenerates at throat when p_{cc} is equal to $p_{inj,sub}^e$. Because of the throat still being choked, the mass flow rate can be computed again via the equation:

$$\dot{m} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{R}} \frac{p_{inj}^{in}}{\sqrt{T_{tank}}} \left(\frac{2}{k+1} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(k-1)}} A_{th}^{inj} \quad [49]$$

3. *the pressure chamber is lower than the limit value $p_{cc,lim}$:*

under this condition, the throat will be choked and the flow will evolve in supersonic conditions along the diverging part of the injector, with an outlet pressure equal to $p_{inj,sup}^e$. If p_{cc} is lower than $p_{inj,sup}^e$, the flow will expand once it has left the injector, if on the other hand p_{cc} is comprised between $p_{cc,lim}$ and $p_{inj,sup}^e$, the flow will recompress through shock waves. Once p_{cc} equals $p_{cc,lim}$, a normal shock-wave will develop at the exit section of the injector. For what concerns the mass flow-rate, being the throat in choked conditions, it assumes the maximum possible value and it can be computed again with eq. (49).

Fig. 4. Distribution of pressures in a converging-diverging nozzle for different flow conditions.

Once the mass flow rate of both propane and hydrogen peroxide are known it is possible to obtain the oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (O/F), that is the ratio between the HTP mass flow rate over the propane mass flow rate:

$$O/F = \frac{\dot{m}_{HTP}}{\dot{m}_f} \quad [50]$$

The geometric parameters of the model are then adjusted to obtain the desired performance.

5. Performance parameters model

The models introduced earlier provide all the necessary elements for calculating the main performance parameters of the engine, namely thrust and specific impulse. In particular, the thrust is computed as follow:

$$T = \dot{m}_{TOT} \cdot c^* \cdot c_F \quad [51]$$

The total mass flow rate is the one elaborated by the engine nozzle, which is always operating under choking conditions at the throat, therefore it can be theoretically computed as:

$$\dot{m}_{TOT} = \sqrt{\frac{k}{R}} \frac{p_{cc}}{\sqrt{T_{cc}}} \left(\frac{2}{k+1} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2(k-1)}} A_{th} \quad [52]$$

The characteristic velocity c^* is computed as:

$$c^* = \frac{\sqrt{kRT_{cc}}}{k \sqrt{\left(\frac{2}{k+1} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{k-1}}}} \quad [53]$$

and is then multiplied by the combustion efficiency. The thrust coefficient c_F is computed as:

$$c_F = \sqrt{\frac{2k^2}{k-1} \left(\frac{2}{k+1} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{k-1}} \left[1 - \left(\frac{p_e}{p_{cc}} \right)^{\frac{k-1}{k}} \right]} + \left(\frac{p_e - p_a}{p_{cc}} \right) \varepsilon \quad [54]$$

where p_e is the pressure at the exit section of the nozzle, p_a is the ambient pressure, which is supposed to be zero as the system will be operating in vacuum, and ε is the nozzle expansion ratio. The $\frac{p_e}{p_{cc}}$ ratio is computed thanks to the gas-dynamic relations for an isentropic flow:

$$\frac{p_e}{p_{cc}} = \left(1 + \frac{k-1}{2} M_e^2 \right)^{\frac{-k}{k-1}} \quad [55]$$

where the Mach number at the exit section of the nozzle is computed by solving the area law (46). The thrust coefficient is then multiplied by the nozzle efficiency.

Once the thrust has been computed, the specific impulse is obtained as:

$$I_{sp} = \frac{T}{\dot{m}_{TOT} \cdot g_0} \quad [56]$$

The formula that describes the predicted combustion chamber pressure is:

$$p_{cc} = \frac{\dot{m}_{TOT} \cdot c^*}{A_{th}} \quad [57]$$

6. Results discussion

Given a predetermined initial tank temperature, it is fundamental to understand how much thermal power needs to be provided to the fuel in the tank for the dis-

charge pressure to be constant over time, ensuring a constant performance. A second point is to analyse how the system performances, particularly thrust, vary with the initial temperature of the tank when a certain thermal power is supplied to it. The operational thermal range of the engine has been selected to be comprised between 10 °C and 50 °C.

From the mission analysis, a 100m/s Δv was determined as necessary for deorbit. However, it was decided to size the system for 200m/s in order to have a higher margin and to allow the platform to have some motion capability in orbit. Based on the previous requirements, a 40 N total thrust was deemed viable for the whole propulsion system [3][10]. Considering 120 kg of mass for the full platform, 200 m/s corresponds to a total impulse of 240 kNs. For 40 N of nominal thrust this translates in 600 s of nominal firing time. As 40 N represents the total nominal thrust, each thruster will produce a nominal thrust of 10 N. To summarise, the initial requirements taken into account to preliminary size the thrusters are the following ones:

- the nominal thrust of $T = 10$ N;
- the nominal burning time of $t_b = 600$ s;
- the propane temperature in the tank between 10 °C and 50 °C;
- the nominal combustion chamber pressure p_{cc} . It was initially set equal to 3 bar, but the exact value has to be determined based on the model results and specifically on the propane and HTP pressures after having computed the pressure losses. Indeed, while it is desirable to maximise the pressure in the combustion chamber to enhance the combustion process, on the other hand, it must not surpass a specific limit value. In fact, beyond this limit, the injectors would no longer be choked in the throat and the mass flow rates could be affected by the oscillations of the combustion chamber pressure;
- an expansion ratio of the nozzle equal to $\varepsilon = 60$

Another parameter that has to be fixed is the oxidizer-to-fuel ratio (O/F). From thermochemical calculations (see Fig. 5, which considers a conservative I_{sp} efficiency of 90%), it is determined that the maximum I_{sp} value for a combustion chamber pressure of 3 bar occurs at about an O/F equal to 7.5 and is around 290 s.

Now, the total mass flow rate can be computed from eq. 56, while the mass flow rate of propane and of HTP are derived as follow:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{m}_f = \frac{\dot{m}_{TOT}}{O/F+1} \\ \dot{m}_{HTP} = \dot{m}_f \cdot O/F \end{cases} \quad [58]$$

Fig. 5. Specific impulse as function of the O/F ratio for different combustion chamber pressures.

Once the combustion chamber pressure has been defined, the nozzle throat area can be computed. For what concern the throat area of the fuel injector into the combustion chamber $A_{th,inj}^f$, it has been obtained by supposing choking conditions and therefore by inverting eq. (49) in which p_{inj}^{in} has been obtained with (47) and (16). The same concept applies for the throat area of the HTP injector. The expansion ratio of both the injectors has been computed by resolving the isentropic relation (46) and by deriving the Mach number at the exit section from the imposition of the exit velocities:

$$\begin{cases} M_{e,f} = \frac{v_{inj,f}}{\sqrt{k_f \cdot R_f \cdot T_f}} \\ M_{e,HTP} = \frac{v_{inj,HTP}}{\sqrt{k_{HTP} \cdot R_{HTP} \cdot T_{HTP}}} \end{cases} \quad [59]$$

where the values for the hydrogen peroxide consider the decomposition gases.

Once the more relevant geometrical parameters of the thruster have been set, the attention is focused on observing the evolution of the system over time with the geometrical features just determined. First, the pressure tank behaviour will be discussed. For what has been previously stated, if no thermal power is supplied to the tank, the temperature will decrease over time, and along with it, the pressure of the tank itself, as the saturation pressure is a function of the temperature. With an increasing initial tank temperature, the mass fraction at which the liquid discharge stops increases (Fig. 6). In other words, the quantity of propane residues remaining in the tank increases, shifting from a residual mass of propane equivalent to

Fig. 6. Tank pressure fraction as function of tank mass fraction for different initial tank temperatures with no thermal power supplied.

5.8% of the initial mass at a starting temperature of 10 °C to a residual mass of 12.8% at 50 °C. The reason why this occurs is that the density of the vapour phase of propane increases with higher initial temperatures. Therefore, the mass of vapour that needs to be generated to preserve the saturation pressure at the same expelled volume of HTP and liquid propane is higher. This observation proves useful for the determination of the quantity of liquid propane that has to be initially loaded into the tank. The essential requirement to fulfil is the complete extraction of the HTP from the tank, regardless of the initial temperature of the tank within the operative temperature range previously defined. Failure to achieve this would result in the accumulation of HTP residual mass that would not be utilised. The risk, in fact, is that at higher temperatures, propane reaches a vapour quality equal to one before the entire quantity of HTP has been expelled. To prevent such a scenario, the mass of the required propane residues has to be added to the nominal liquid propane mass. Specifically, the mass of propane residues added is the one obtained by simulating a discharge at the initial temperature of 50 °C without supplying thermal power to the tank and with an initial liquid propane mass equal to the nominal one. This ensures that for all initial temperatures below 50 °C, the HTP mass is completely extracted. It is important that the loaded mass of HTP is computed considering only the nominal liquid

propane mass. After the previous considerations, the nominal liquid propane mass will be equal to:

$$m_{f,l} = \dot{m}_f \cdot t_b = 0.24 \text{ kg} \quad [60]$$

while the nominal residual mass of propane to be added is the 12.8% of the previous value, that is $m_{f,l}^{res} = 0.031 \text{ kg}$.

As already anticipated, the additional propane residuals, differently from the HTP ones, can be exploited by the cold-gas thrusters after the burn for the attitude control and that is a further reason why is more convenient having propane residuals left rather than HTP ones.

If we then analyse the tank pressure evolution over time, still without providing any thermal power, another aspect emerges. Specifically, with an increase in the tank initial temperature, the discharge completion time decreases (Fig. 7). The reason for this is that higher initial temperatures correspond to higher propane saturation pressures. Therefore, if the tank pressure is higher, the propellant outflow rate will also be higher together with thrust, justifying the reduced time required for the discharge completion.

Fig. 7. Tank pressure as function of time for different tank temperatures with no thermal power supplied.

As already anticipated, the main consequence of having a variable pressure over time in the tank is that the system performance does not remain constant at nominal levels. The thrust is initially equal to 10 N, but then it decreases and it falls below 7 N at the end of the tank discharge, for a 10 °C initial temperature (Fig. 8). This is a

direct consequence of the fact that the mass flow rates of both propane and HTP decrease with respect to their initially assumed nominal values. On the other hand, the O/F ratio remains nearly constant over time, thanks to the linear choking conditions of the injectors. If the O/F ratio remains almost constant, then the specific impulse likewise stays nearly unchanged (lower than 1% variation).

Fig. 8. Thrust vs time for a starting tank temperature of 10 °C at different heating powers.

From the results of the model it is possible to make a few other observations. First of all, from the calculations it has emerged that, as the initial temperature of the tank increases, the thermal power required to achieve a constant discharge over time also increases. For example, the power needed at 30 °C is 1.67 times the one required at 10 °C. Simultaneously, there is also an increase in the additional mass of propane that needs to be loaded. However, there is also an improvement in the combustion chamber pressure, with a positive effect on combustion. Finally, for the same thruster geometry, higher temperatures/pressures provide higher thrusts and shorter burning times. An attempt has been made to find a compromise between a tank pressure that is sufficiently high, to ensure a chamber pressure not too low, and the supplied thermal power to the tank.

For this reason, to save power, it has been decided to fix the minimum operational temperature at 10 °C with a power supply able to keep (with margins) the pressure constant at this temperature (Fig. 8), accepting a decreasing

profile at higher temperatures until the tank temperature falls down to its fixed minimum value. The system is foreseen to operate only when temperatures are equal or higher than 10 °C. If this is not the case, heaters can be turned on to reach the minimum required pressure before firing.

The propane loading has been calculated in order to guarantee a complete HTP discharge at any initial temperature.

Regarding thrust, the 10 N requirement has been imposed at the minimum operational temperature as this is the case that provides the minimum thrust and longer burning time.

The model yields the following temperature-thrust relations:

Temperature	Thrust
10°C	10 N
30°C	15 N
50°C	20 N

7. Conclusion

The EARS spacecraft propulsion subsystem has been designed to use the propellant combination HTP-propane. Both propellants are self-pressurized by the propane vapour pressure. A full model of the propulsion subsystem has been implemented. It simulates the HTP and propane discharges from their tanks, considering their pressure losses along the respective fluidic lines, keeping into account their choked gaseous injections into the combustion chamber. The propane simulation was also integrated with a boiling model to design the regenerative channel used to vaporise the fuel while the HTP is decomposed through a catalyst. The ultimate goal was to determine the dependency of the system behavior on the initial tank temperature and to find out the thermal power required to stabilise the tank discharge, and ultimately the thrust over time, thus enabling the optimization of the engine performance during operation in the selected temperature range.

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